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The Recurring Great Atlantic Sargassum Belt Impacts the Caribbean and South Florida

Fig. 1. MODIS satellite image of Sargassum transport from the Caribbean through the Yucatan Channel and into the Loop Current and Florida Current on July 16, 2020

Since 2011, the floating brown seaweeds known as pelagic *Sargassum* have formed a *Great Atlantic Sargassum Belt* (GASB) in the tropical Atlantic Ocean extending between Africa and South America [1]. The GASB represents an expansion in the distribution of this unique floating vegetation, which was historically restricted to the Gulf of Mexico (GOM), Loop Current, Gulf Stream, Sargasso Sea, and Caribbean Sea (Fig. 1). This vegetation was first reported by Christopher Columbus in the Sargasso Sea in 1492 and includes two pelagic species – *Sargassum natans* and *Sargassum fluitans* - that reproduce by vegetative fragmentation (Fig. 2). Early oceanographers were impressed with the vigorous appearance of *Sargassum* in the Sargasso Sea and estimated that ~ 90% of this vegetation was comprised of *S. natans* with the remainder being *S. fluitans* and several benthic species recruited from shallow coastal waters of the West Indies [2].

The precept that pelagic *Sargassum* flourishes in surface waters of the

Sargasso Sea became a paradox to modern oceanographers who referred to this oligotrophic gyre as a “biological desert” [3]. Studies of the productivity and nutrition of *Sargassum* showed that photosynthesis and growth of these oceanic populations were nutrient-limited in the Sargasso Sea, compared to more productive nutrient-enriched plants in neritic waters of the GOM, Loop Current, and Gulf Stream [4]. These studies documented the importance of nutrient cycling by associated fish and invertebrates within the pelagic *Sargassum* community that has been designated “Essential Fish Habitat” by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). A variety of nutrient sources in neritic waters of the western North Atlantic Ocean and GOM explained the higher nutrient contents and productivity of *Sargassum*, which included shelf-break upwelling, continental runoff via rivers (Mississippi River, Everglades), submarine groundwater discharge, benthic sediment recycling,

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and atmospheric inputs [5]. Human influences on several of these nutrient sources greatly increased in the 1980s and 1990s as a result of increased application of agricultural fertilizers, urbanization, atmospheric pollution, and extreme rainfall and flooding associated with climate change. These

increasing nutrient inputs correlated with increasing accumulations of *Sargassum* on beaches and shorelines around the GOM [5].

A variety of nutrient sources appear to also be supporting the development of the GASB in the tropical Atlantic Ocean since 2011. Studies using

MERIS (Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer) and MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) satellite remote sensing described a new *Sargassum* bloom event north of the Amazon River in April 2011, which by July had spread eastward to Africa and westward to the Lesser Antilles and Caribbean Sea [6]. With the exception of 2013, the GASB has since formed annually, developing during spring months and peaking in abundance in summer; in July 2018, the GASB extended for 8,850 km from Africa to the GOM and ranked as the largest algae bloom on earth [1]. Over its broad distribution, the GASB can be supported by nutrients from the Amazon, Orinoco, and Congo rivers, upwelling in the eastern tropical Atlantic off the African coast [1,7,8], and atmospheric deposition of Saharan dust and biomass burning in South Africa [9]. Annual flooding events in the Amazon basin since 2009 combined with increased nutrient supply from deforestation and fertilizer use are factors potentially supporting bloom initiation in the central western Atlantic Ocean in 2011 [1,6,8,10].

The excessive *Sargassum* biomass transported from the GASB to coastal waters in the Caribbean region have been causing a myriad of environmental impacts. Offshore, the extreme abundance of *Sargassum* has fouled fishing gear and caused challenges for safe navigation in and around the extensive mats. Decreased catches of the dolphinfish or mahi mahi (*Coryphaena hippurus*; -37%) and flying fish (family Exocoetidae; -52%) have been reported in Barbados. After stranding on beaches and coastlines, decomposition of *Sargassum* releases large amounts of brown leachate and results in hypoxia and anoxia, releasing toxic hydrogen sulphide and ammonia. The resulting water quality degradation from *Sargassum* exacerbates coastal eutrophication, resulting in fish kills, sea turtle mortality, and increased die-off of seagrasses and corals [11]. The massive influx of *Sargassum* to the Mesoamerican reef system was identified as a contributing cause of decreasing water quality and the outbreak in stony coral tissue loss disease (SCTLD) in 2018 [12].

As in the Caribbean, *Sargassum* influx to South Florida has increased

Fig. 2. Collection of *Sargassum natans* (left side of photo) and *Sargassum fluitans* (right side of photo) off Ft. Pierce, Florida, for nutrient analysis

Fig. 3. *Sargassum* influx to the south side of Big Pine Key in the lower Florida Keys, June, 2014. Note absence of abundant fishes associated with *Sargassum* in the bottom photo

Fig 4. *Sargassum* stranding event on the south side of the Ft. Pierce inlet, Ft. Pierce, Florida, July, 2020

since 2011, especially following the larger size of the GASB after 2014 [1]. Extensive mats of *Sargassum* washed ashore in the Florida Keys between May and August 2014 (Fig. 3), a trend that has continued through summer of 2020 (Fig. 4). The massive strandings and decomposition have impaired water quality in nearshore waters of South Florida, especially in coastal bays and canals where *Sargassum* can become concentrated (Fig 4). Since 2014, SCTLD has spread from Miami through the Florida Keys during the same time frame when *Sargassum* influx has increased. This correlation parallels research in the Caribbean that has linked increasing *Sargassum* influx to worsening water quality and coral reef health [12].

Public health issues related to the increasing *Sargassum* influx have also increased in recent years. During large-scale strandings in the summer of 2018, more than 11,400 residents in Martinique and Guadeloupe were diagnosed with acute exposure to toxic H₂S gas produced by decaying *Sargassum* [13]. Additionally, bacterial (fecal coliform, enterococcus) and heavy metal (arsenic, cadmium) pollution associated with excessive *Sargassum* strandings are causing concern for recreational beach use, as well as attempts to safely dispose of *Sargassum* or recycle its biomass into fertilizers and soil conditioners for use on food crops.

The serious environmental and public health issues resulting from the harmful *Sargassum* influx pose major economic challenges to the Caribbean and South Florida region. *Sargassum*

removal from Texas beaches during earlier, less severe inundations was estimated at \$2.9 million per year. In 2018, the Caribbean-wide clean-up cost \$210 million [8] and Florida's Miami-Dade County alone estimated removal expenses of \$45 million in 2019. In addition, the direct economic impacts to tourism and commercial fishing are substantial, underscoring the urgent need for research focused on the various physical, chemical, and biological mechanisms underlying the development of the GASB.

The United Nations Environment Program (UNEP - GPNM) in collaboration with IOC UNESCO and the IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB programme hosted four webinars on *Sargassum* in 2020, and the Secretariat has shared the current realities of the impacts and approaches being taken to address the issue. Various stakeholder groups participating in the webinars have expressed their concern for the recurring *Sargassum* events in West Africa and the Caribbean region, highlighting the necessity for mainstreaming the issue in the policy arena, possibly a resolution at the United Nations Environment Assembly.

The scale of the GASB, which extends from Africa to the GOM and South Florida, is unprecedented for a HAB, as is the complexity of physical, chemical, and biological factors supporting initiation, seasonal development, and transport of the GASB.

Recently, the Scientific Steering Committee of the IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB Programme, through its Science and Implementation Plan, has recognized

the *Sargassum* expansion as an emerging HAB issue. A new subcommittee dedicated to this topic has been established (see GlobalHAB this issue)

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Ciguatera fish poisoning event in New Zealand from imported tropical reef fish and confirmation of Pacific ciguatoxins by LC-MS/MS

Ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP) is an illness caused by the consumption of fish contaminated with ciguatoxins (CTXs) and possibly maitotoxins (MTXs). The causative organism is a single-celled alga in the genus *Gambierdiscus* (Dinophyceae). *Gambierdiscus* is epiphytic on macroalgae, eel grasses and coral and is consumed with the host substrate by herbivorous and coral grazing fish. These fish are predated upon by omnivorous and carnivorous reef fish species and the ciguatoxins are bioaccumulated and biotransformed up the marine food web [1].

The only known Pacific-CTX (P-CTX) producer in New Zealand waters is *G. polynesiensis*, which has been isolated from Rangitāhua/Kermadec Islands (a New Zealand territory). This toxic dinoflagellate species is common throughout the tropical Pacific Islands. A related genus, *Fukuyoa* (previously named *Gambierdiscus*), has been isolated from

the Bay of Islands, but does not produce P-CTXs.

Both genera were considered sub-tropical to tropical, but in recent years *G. carpenteri* has been isolated from the temperate waters south of Sydney, NSW, Australia. Cases of CFP in Australia have historically been reported from Queensland waters but, with warming ocean temperatures causing changes in the prevailing currents, and expansion of the sub-tropical and temperate latitudes, fish caught in NSW waters have caused CFP in that state. The risk of locally contracted cases of CFP occurring in New Zealand is therefore greater as the coastal waters around New Zealand continue to warm and as some species become adapted to cooler waters [1].

Cases of CFP reported in New Zealand to date have resulted from the consumption of contaminated reef fish (including eels) by tourists who have

returned to New Zealand after consuming reef fish in the Pacific Islands and then become ill, or from New Zealanders consuming imported reef fish they have brought back into New Zealand themselves or have purchased from a commercial vendor. Several cases of CFP, linked to the consumption of Moray eel brought back from Samoa, were reported in Wellington, New Zealand, in 2016 [2]. Another series of cases were clinically diagnosed, based on symptomatology, in 2019 following the consumption of Moray eel brought back from the Kingdom of Tonga and home-smoked [3]. No cases of CFP due to consumption of locally caught and consumed fish have been reported.

In May 2020 there was another intoxication event when five people from two families became ill after the consumption of reef fish, reported to be Fiji Kawakawa (*Epinephelus* sp.). There were three males aged between 19 and 58 and two females, one in her 40s and the other in her 50s. The symptoms were typical of CFP (inversion of hot and cold, paraesthesia and dysaesthesia) and the patients were clinically diagnosed as suffering from CFP. Immediately following the report, a product recall was put in place to try and prevent any additional intoxications occurring (Fig. 1).

Two samples of meal remnants, fried fish and fish curry (imported as *Epinephelus* sp.; Fig. 2), were received at Cawthron Institute, 2 June 2020. The results of analyses, as reported to the Canterbury District Health Board, indicated quantifiable levels of P-CTX-1B and two additional fish metabolite P-CTXs (Table 1). The samples had the skin and bones removed prior to being homogenised in their entirety. Analysis was carried out in duplicate using an in-house quantitative LC-MS/MS method for P-CTXs and MTXs [4]. The LoQ for P-CTX-1B was 0.1 µg/kg. Three other P-CTX fish metabolites, 52-epi-54-deoxyCTX-1B (P-CTX-2), 54-deoxyCTX-1B (P-CTX-3) and 51-hydroxy-CTX-3C were reported by presence/absence. Results for P-CTX-1B were adjusted based on the spike recovery (45% and 48% respectively).

In the Pacific region P-CTX-1B has been well documented in many fish species [5] and is the typically dominant P-CTX analogue detected from

Krazy Price Mart Ltd frozen camouflage grouper (kawakawa)

27 May 2020: Krazy Price Mart Ltd is recalling a specific batch of its frozen camouflage grouper (kawakawa) due to the presence of ciguatoxin, which may cause ciguatera poisoning if eaten.

Product identification	
Product type	Frozen whole fish (gutted)
Name of product	Camouflage grouper (kawakawa)
Batch marking	The fish is not labelled.
Date marking	No date marks appear on this product. The product was available for sale between 10 March and 21 May 2020
Package size and description	The product is sold as an individual whole fish (gutted) wrapped in clear plastic.
Distribution	The product is imported from Fiji. The product is sold only at Krazy Price Mart Ltd in Christchurch.
Notes	This recall does not affect any other Krazy Price Mart products.

Fig. 1. Notification of recall of product due to ciguatera fish poisoning cases in New Zealand

intoxication events. No regulatory limits have been officially set for CTXs, although the FDA has an established action level of 0.01 µg/kg P-CTX-1B equivalents for Pacific CTXs and 0.1 µg/kg C-CTX-1 equivalents for Caribbean CTXs [6]. Two additional fish imported in the same batch as the recalled product were also tested but were negative for P-CTXs (Fig. 3). Upon receipt these additional fish were identified as two different species – Camouflage Grouper (*Epinephelus polyphekadion*; Fig. 3) and Squaretail Grouper (*Plectropomus areolatus*; Fig. 4). The fact these fish were imported as a single species demonstrates the complications associated with species identification and linking intoxication events to a particular species. In addition, as these fish were not toxic and caught in the same area, it illustrates the complexities associated with ciguatera fish poisoning and the determination of risk fish species. It is always desirable therefore to get meal remnants so that analytical testing can confirm the clinical diagnosis.

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Table 1. Concentrations of P-CTX-1B recorded in reef fish samples (imported as *Epinephelus* sp.) linked to a ciguatera fish poisoning event in Christchurch, New Zealand.

Sample type	P-CTX-1B (µg/kg)	P-CTX-2	P-CTX-3	51-hydroxy-CTX-3C
Fried fish	0.29	Present	Present	Absent
Curried fish	0.21	Present	Present	Absent

Fig. 2. Remnants of fish meals linked to ciguatera fish poisoning in Christchurch, New Zealand. Remnants contained ciguatoxins

Fig. 3. Camouflage Grouper (*Epinephelus polyphekadion*) imported in the same batch of fish that caused the ciguatera fish poisoning event. This fish was negative for Pacific ciguatoxins

Fig. 4. Squaretail Grouper (*Plectropomus areolatus*) imported in the same batch of fish that caused the ciguatera fish poisoning event. This fish was negative for Pacific ciguatoxins

First report of *Ostreopsis* in a tropical mangrove lagoon in São Tomé Island (Gulf of Guinea)

Fig. 1. Location of a) S. Tomé Island in the Gulf of Guinea (African Continent), b) the Malanza lagoon (0°02'46"N, 6°31'48"E) at the south of S. Tomé Island, and c) the sampling station (M1) in Malanza lagoon.

We report for the first time the presence of *Ostreopsis* in a tropical mangrove lagoon of the São Tomé and Príncipe Archipelago (Gulf of Guinea).

In-situ sampling was performed during the rainy season in November

2014 at the Malanza mangrove system. This is located in São Tomé Obô Natural Park (PNOT) in the southernmost part of the São Tomé Island (0°02'46"N, 6°31'48"E) [1]. The Malanza lagoon is a nutrient-enriched mangrove system

with a central basin connected with off-shore seawater through a constricted inlet [1] (Fig. 1). Water samples were collected by hauling a plankton net (20 µm mesh size) horizontally at the lagoon inlet (station M1 location in Fig. 1). Samples were collected during a flood when the landward current was relatively strong. Water samples were then stored in 125 ml glass bottles and preserved with neutral Lugol's iodine solution. The sampling site was 2.2m deep and at the time of sampling, the water temperature was 27.3 °C and salinity 29.1.

The morphology of isolated single cells stained with the fluorochrome Calcofluor White [2] were characterized under the light microscope (Olympus BX50), using bright field and epifluorescence microscopy. Tentative identification to species level was made according to Penna et al. [3]. All cells (n=6) were oval shaped and anterioposteriorly compressed (Fig. 2), with dorso-ventral diameters ranging from 39.40 - 51.48 µm and width from 28.75 - 34.91 µm (Table 1). Thecal pores were only of one type (Fig. 3). The apical pore (Po) measured less than ca 8.5 µm (n=2). Given the occurrence of cryptic species in the genus *Ostreopsis*, an identification based only on morphological characteristics is not sufficient and further work using molecular tools, to confirm

Fig. 2. *Ostreopsis* sp. bright field (a) and epifluorescence (b–f) micrographs. Epitheca (b) and hypotheca (c and e) showing plate patterns. Apical pore plate (Po) (d). Side view of *Ostreopsis* sp. (f). Po, apical pore plate. Scale bar = 20 µm. For cell size, see Table 1.

Table 1. Morphometric characteristics of *Ostreopsis* cells (n=6) analyzed in this study. Dorso-ventral diameter and width (including mean \pm standard deviation values).

Dorso-ventral diameter (μm)	mean \pm standard deviation	Width (μm)	mean \pm standard deviation
48.44	45.44 \pm 4.075	34.91	32.47 \pm 2.215
39.40		28.75	
45.99		31.95	
41.31		30.83	
51.48		34.83	
46.00		33.53	

the species identification is required.

Ostreopsis cells were detected in the Malanza lagoon in a station located close to the ocean (M1). *Ostreopsis* is an epiphytic-benthic dinoflagellate genus which colonizes a variety of substrates including macroalgae, rocky and soft sediments and coral reefs. Cells belonging to this genus can also occur in the water column usually associated with higher concentrations of benthic cells [4]. In this study, free living *Ostreopsis* cells were collected from the water column, suggesting that their presence may be the result of a high benthic cell concentration inside the lagoon. Another hypothesis is that it may arise from a cell resuspension and transport mechanism, probably associated with the high tide water flow from offshore into the lagoon. The presence of coral reefs that represent potential habitats for benthic dinoflagellates were observed along the coastal zone. Further work is needed to clarify whether the species is present inside the lagoon or if it has been transported from the adjacent coastal zone.

Species within the genus *Ostreopsis* produce potent neurotoxins belonging to the palytoxin group which have been related to serious human poisoning through the consumption of toxin-containing seafood [5] and the aerosolization of toxins [6]. *Ostreopsis* is often associated with other nuisance dinoflagellate genera such as *Gambierdiscus*, *Coolia*, *Prorocentrum* and *Am-*

Fig. 3. *Ostreopsis* sp. from the Malanza lagoon. Epifluorescence microscopy, showing the plate pores.

phidium, which can develop benthic harmful algal blooms (BHABs), causing severe problems in economically relevant activities such as fishing and tourism. BHABs have become a major concern because of their biogeographical expansion from endemic tropical and subtropical areas to temperate areas. To date, there are no previous reports on the occurrence of BHAB species in São Tomé Island. The presence of *Ostreopsis* sp. cells in the water column of the Malanza mangrove system highlights the need for further studies on the distribution and ecology of this species.

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The impact of toxic *Dinophysis* spp. on the productivity of Scottish shellfish farms

Fig. 1: Map of the Scottish marine regions. Shellfish farms considered in this study are located in the Western Scotland (Clyde, Clyde, Outer Hebrides and Shetland Islands) (Credit Scottish Gov).

There is limited evidence in the peer-reviewed literature on the monetary impacts of Harmful Algal Blooms (HAB) on European aquaculture. Direct estimates of damage, sensitive information for businesses, are not easily disclosed, and independent studies from public sector are limited, if not missing. The Scottish shellfish sector is not an exception. However, revealing and possibly mitigating likely damages on production caused by HABs is an important goal because of the social and economic importance played by aquaculture for rural communities characterized by limited job opportunities. For instance, in the Scottish Highlands, shellfish farming is carried out predominantly by small family enterprises generating a gross value (turnover) of £12.4m [1]. This sector is composed of 205 separate enterprises that support, in rural coastal areas, more than 300 employees mainly involved in the production of Blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) (~96% by weight of the total shellfish production) [2] with a value (turnover) of £ 10.1

m in 2017 [1;3]. While this turnover might be considered of low relevance in comparison with other industries, it is very important for the sustainable development of the local economy and the protection of jobs. Realising this importance, the Scottish Government is supportive of doubling the industry's economic value and the number of jobs by 2030. However, to achieve this goal, a series of technical and environmental issues should be resolved: among these an accurate valuation of factors that are limiting the current shellfish production.

In Scottish waters, Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning (DSP), Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP) and Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP) are the shellfish toxicity syndromes of greatest concern [4;5]. PSP toxins produced by the genus *Alexandrium* are regularly detected in mussels during the summer months [6], while DSP toxins are more frequent still, often as a result of the advective transport of the causative *Dinophysis* to coastal aquaculture [7;8] (Fig. 2), with *Prorocentrum lima* being

another source of these toxins. *Pseudo-nitzschia* mediated ASP is less frequent [9] and may also require advective cell transport [10].

To ensure shellfish safety for public consumption, EU regulation EC No 853/2004 requires the monitoring of the concentration of biotoxins in shellfish flesh and their causative harmful phytoplankton. In Scottish waters, sampling is undertaken weekly during spring and summer, and fortnightly in winter and autumn at a set of Representative Monitoring Points (RMP) with the aim of minimising the risk of not detecting biotoxin concentrations above regulatory threshold shellfish [11]. Monitoring is overseen by the competent authority Food Standards Scotland (FSS), and carried out by the Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture Science (CEFAS) for biotoxins and the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS) for phytoplankton. If biotoxin concentrations at the relevant RMP exceed regulatory threshold, the farms associated with this RMP are closed to harvesting and risk management procedures based on phytoplankton and biotoxin data from the current and previous four weeks are used to determine the appropriate harvesting action. Mussels can be left in place to depurate toxins naturally and reach health and safety conditions required by the market. However, because much of Scottish shellfish production fulfils commercial contracts to supply a particular quantity of product at a certain time, it is likely that this product will go out of phase with market demand and remain unsold.

While considerable effort is expended to ensure shellfish safety, the impact of HABs on the economic sustainability of this regionally important industry remains unquantified. Statistics shows that mussel production in Western Scotland regions (Fig. 1) has been quite stable during the period 2009-2018 at an average of nearly 7,200 tonnes per year. The lowest production occurred in 2013 (6,935 tonnes), and the highest in 2016 (10,586) carried out in nearly 160 active sites employing globally 330 workers. The region that exhibits the highest production is the Shetland Islands with 4,825 tonnes, followed by West Highlands (850 tonnes), Clyde

(843 tonnes) and Outer Hebrides (678 tonnes). The Shetland Islands is the region characterised by the highest capital-intensive production with 75 sites employing in total 112 staff.

Using a production function approach applied to a panel data of mussel farms in the four most productive Scottish shellfish harvesting regions (Shetland Islands, West Highlands, Outer Hebrides and Clyde) (Fig. 1) over the period 2009-2018, we have estimated the impact of DSP on shellfish industry production [12]. We found that at the average DSP biotoxin concentration of 24% above the safe threshold, recorded in the period of investigation, these toxins are expected to cause a yearly average reduction of nearly 15% in production (95% confidence interval -20% to -10%). This is equivalent to a loss of 1,080 ton of shellfish per year (95% confidence interval -1,490 ton to -670 ton). At the average price of £ 1,272 per ton (in 2015 constant GBP), the average annual economic damage caused by DSP is equivalent to £ 1.37m (95% confidence interval £-1.9m to

Fig. 2. Electron micrograph of *Dinophysis* sp. (Credit Callum Whyte, SAMS)

£-0.85m) over a turnover of approximately £ 10.1m. Our results offer insight into likely regional differences in operation and environmental characteristics of the sites. In the West Highlands, characterized by a lower productivity than Shetland Islands, the impact on production is marginally more damaging, suggesting that managers consider strategies to minimize the impacts of harmful algae, from shifting production sites to rearranging contractual agreements

with wholesalers and retailers. The full study has recently been published in Harmful Algae [12].

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Fig. 3. Mussel farming in Scotland. Top: Shellfish longlines in a Scottish sea loch, Bottom: a long line being raised

Bloom of *Cylindrotheca closterium* originating from shrimp farming discharges in the SE Gulf of Mexico

Fig. 1. Location of sampling sites (S1-S8) in coastal waters of Campeche (red frame), Peninsula de Yucatán, SE Gulf of Mexico.

Discharges from shrimp farming into the sea are common in the coastal zone of Campeche, located on the western side of the Yucatán Peninsula, SE Gulf of Mexico (Fig. 1). These discharges, with heavy loads of nutrients added to stimulate phytoplankton production, are a major source of eutrophication [1]. Despite the environmental impact of these activities in shrimp cultivation areas in the Caribbean, very little information is available on the

phytoplankton species composition within the discharge waters. A project was carried out to identify anthropogenic impacts along the central coast of Campeche. The project included a study of phytoplankton species composition, with an emphasis on potentially harmful species. Eight sampling stations (depths ca. 50 cm) from three coastal localities (City of Campeche, Seybaplaya and Champotón) corresponding to sites affected by anthropogenic inputs were chosen (Fig. 1). These stations were sampled in September and November 2016. A bloom of the pennate diatom *Cylindrotheca closterium* (Ehrenb.) Reimann & J.C. Lewin, with a maximum of 1.4×10^5 cells L^{-1} , was observed in September. The maximum cell density was found at station S4, a drainage area for shrimp farming discharges (Fig. 1). Environmental conditions in this station at the time of sample collection were: salinity 41.5, temperature 31.5°C, pH=9.2 and dissolved oxygen 7.1 mg L^{-1} . Water discoloration was observed (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Water discoloration from a bloom of *Cylindrotheca closterium* observed in September 2016 in shrimp farming discharge waters in Campeche, SE Gulf of Mexico.

Cylindrotheca closterium, a well known bloom-forming species, has been reported in high cell densities in the SE Gulf of Mexico [2]. In coastal

waters of northern Yucatan, the species is present in high numbers throughout the year. Blooms have been observed mainly during the warmer rainy season from mid-May to mid-October [3]. Our observations are in agreement with these results. In Yucatan waters, especially in the marinas, *C. closterium* blooms appear to be linked to high concentrations of nitrite, phosphate, nitrate and urea. These phytoplankton blooms are indicators of eutrophication due to fluctuations in environmental conditions because of the intensity and type of human activities occurring in the study area. The species is ubiquitous, has a high potential to dominate both planktonic and benthic microalgal assemblages, and is characterized by its high growth, reproduction rates and its wide geographical distribution.

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New GlobalHAB Theme: Sargassum Blooms

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

Intergovernmental
Oceanographic
Commission

International Council for Science
Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research

The GlobalHAB Science and Implementation Plan (www.globalhab.info) identifies that new, emerging HAB related issues can be incorporated into the program. This has been the case with the Sargassum mass occurrences in the Caribbean and the west coast of Africa (Fig. 1). In 2020 GlobalHAB established a subcommittee to develop the new GlobalHAB topic. The subcommittee is comprised of four experts on *Sargassum* and macroalgae ecology, Brigitta van Tussenbroek (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico), Brian Lapointe (Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institute, Florida, US), Ester Serrao (University of Algarve, Portugal) and José E. Martinelli Filho (Federal University of Pará, Brazil) (Fig. 2) and, from the GlobalHAB Scientific Steering Committee itself, Raffaele Siano (Ifremer, France) and Elisa Berdalet (ICM, Spain). The subcommittee may expand with new members to cover additional scientific aspects and geographic regions as required.

The overall task of the subcommittee is to contribute to the identification of the key research questions to understand *Sargassum* growth dynamics, and to develop long term preventive measures, adequate forecasting and warning systems for *Sargassum* beaching. To achieve this objective, the subcommittee is organizing an Open Science Meeting (OSM) where the international scientific community working on *Sargassum* related issues is invited to participate. The OSM will facilitate a thorough review of current

Fig. 1. *Sargassum* accumulation on sea turtle nesting beaches in Guinea-Bissau, Bijagós Islands. Photo from the Instituto da Biodiversidade e das Áreas Protegidas (IBAP, Guinea-Bissau)

knowledge on *Sargassum* dynamics and identify research and technology development priorities. This will be achieved through expert workshops as part of the OSM addressing key questions. The results will be published as a white paper and possible peer reviewed papers. The OSM will also help identify the need and focus for further activities to enhance the general knowledge of the biology of *Sargassum*, to contribute to capacity building in the area and to support management and mitigation possibilities. A summary of this research plan will be included in the GlobalHAB Science and Implementation Plan.

The *Sargassum* topic is complementary to other ongoing *Sargassum* initiatives in the world. Until now, GlobalHAB has been linked to UNEP and GESAMP activities, collaborating in the organization of four webinars

in 2020. These webinars increased the visibility of the active and multidisciplinary community working on *Sargassum* related issues. Several of the GESAMP sponsoring agencies and the European Funded project EuroSea (<https://eurosea.eu>) have shown an interest in the topic and the OSM. The OSM on *Sargassum* will be hosted by the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico. Due to COVID-19 the OSM is planned for 2022.

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Fig. 2. Members of the new GlobalHAB *Sargassum* subcommittee. From left to right: Brigitta van Tussenbroek, Brian Lapointe, Ester Serrao and José E. Martinelli Filho

Insights from the first US HAB Symposium Science Communication Workshop

The 10th US Symposium on Harmful Algae was held November 3-8, 2019, in beautiful Orange Beach, Alabama – hosted jointly by researchers from the University of South Alabama, Dauphin Island Sea Lab, Auburn University and the University of Oklahoma. This was the first US HAB meeting to host a Science Communication workshop, and it was such a success the hope is to continue with these at future meetings. A broad panel of experts was assembled to discuss their unique vantage points for communicating HAB science, including approaches to research, translation of research findings, testifying before Congress about the importance of HABs, and integrating information about HABs into weather forecasts. While these are all unique opportunities for communication, they share the same challenges in providing concise, clear, but non-alarmist, messaging regarding the human health, ecological, and socioeconomic impacts of HAB

events. The goal of the workshop was to identify the tools available for participants to communicate HAB science in their respective regions.

Legislative landscapes are inherently complex and perplexing environments, as they require navigating both scientific and political factors. However, common ground can be found with the proper preparation, engagement, and approach. When conveying your message to political representatives, it is important to understand the legislative process and assemble your HAB colleagues (locally, regionally, nationally as appropriate) into a unified voice (involving your institutional liaison if available) and remain active throughout the entire process with letter writing, public commenting, and in-person meetings with representatives and staff (**Peter Hill**). Be prepared for dialogue in various forms, including invited testimony, briefings with staffers, and the quick “elevator speech” for unex-

pected encounters with key people. Messages should be simple, clear, and have succinct “asks” – all supported with pertinent materials, reinforced by post-meeting communications (**Don Anderson**). Whether oral or written, remember to provide the “big picture” compelling stories related to human and economic impacts, and avoid painstaking details and data sets (**Dan Ayres**). Engaging with representatives can be done in a variety of ways, including in-office visits, targeted events like “lobby days,” invitations to visit the lab and/or field site, and offering to be a point person for HAB expertise (**Margaret Lansing**).

Communicating HAB science with **industry** entities can be challenging due to the potential for direct financial damages (particularly long term market impacts) through misunderstandings and alarmist language translated into public perceptions of product safety. Keeping information concise, consistent, and jargon-free supports constructive exchanges between researchers and industry, which, in turn, leads to progress in developing relevant early warning detection systems (**Dan Ayres**). To further these efforts, attend in-

Fig. 1. View of a session during the first US HAB Symposium-Science Communication Workshop

dustly-focused meetings such as those related to the local fishing community or aquaculture.

An educated *media* is vital for effective community response to threats against human health and local economies that arise from HAB activity. Too often, the discussion coincides with an active bloom event when tensions can be high and uncertainties abound. HAB scientists are quickly thrust into a situation where digestible information is being sought by the media and laypeople with diverse backgrounds and interest levels. When called upon, use the communication tips outlined above to share what is and is not known (simple graphics can be highly engaging), provide timely updates as more information becomes available, and describe recommended actions and approaches needed to further knowledge (**Kate Hubbard**). Agencies that are frequently called upon should designate a contact person and develop a written response plan for formulating consistent messaging that provides simple information, void of speculation, for a variety of target audiences (**Heather Raymond**). Inquiries will come from many sectors, therefore extensive documentation and re-visiting communication successes and challenges will aid in refining this plan for future use. When the media do call, be prepared by having written (and practiced!) your talking points ahead of time so you can stay focused and provide concise information during the interview (**Ken Kostel**). Do not feel you have to answer every question, but do offer to help fact-check, ask for a deadline, and follow-up with additional contacts and resources as appropriate.

We are presented with daily opportunities to discuss the impacts of HABs with the *general public* on an individual scale and can do so by identifying connections to the health and well being of communities and families within. The key to success is to empower people of all ages and backgrounds with achievable solutions and ways to become involved. For example, citizen science programs have mutual benefits for the general populace and research programs. By giving citizens a voice, validating their point of view, and having empathy for their situation, we can build strong relationships within and

outside times of crises (**Tracy Fanara**). Building trust and rapport comes through introducing yourself first as a person, then as a scientist. Develop connections through shared interests, and family and community attributes (**Barbara Kirkpatrick**). Working with those in the public sector can further the dissemination of important information, particularly in times of uncertainty. Reach out to these people directly or through social media, as they can help dismiss rumors, translate science jargon, and serve as the voice of reason and provide the 'bottom line' for the lay public (**Ryan Wichman**).

Given that many adults (and even more young people) glean their information from *social media*, it is imperative to develop and refine strategies that are both engaging and constructive. These can be highly useful platforms, but they also lend themselves to providing multiple messaging from various angles (from agencies to citizen journalists). Successful tips for engaging and empowering a broad base of readers include being timely with information, using images and humor where appropriate, providing context while keeping posts concise, remaining personable, asking a question or employing a poll, and including relevant hashtags of collaborators and influencers so the information reaches larger audiences (**Margaret Lansing, Ken Kostel**). These platforms can be used effectively to steer interested parties to translational products, such as newsletters, blog posts, and well developed agency websites with tiered information that allows the user to choose where they want/need to navigate.

Public communication has not been a traditional offering in science disciplines, however the world is now more connected than ever and the delivery of timely, valid and understandable scientific information is of increased importance. The tools highlighted above afford us the unique opportunity to step out from behind the bench and participate in the expanding information network available to help ensure informed citizenry.

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Advances in Colombia to address the Ciguatera problem

In the last two decades, an average of 17 cases of ciguatera poisoning (CP) have been registered each year in the Colombian Caribbean. Given that epidemiological surveillance is not very comprehensive, the number of cases is likely to be much higher. This situation prompted the interest in developing an inter-institutional and inter-sectorial plan in Colombia aimed at monitoring, forecasting and evaluating the risks of CP. The IV International HAB- National HAB Workshop in Colombia was planned to advance the development of the structure and operation of a risk management system.

The organization of the workshop was in charge of several institutions: Colombian Ocean Commission (CCO), Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Institute of Marine and Coastal Research (INVEMAR), General Maritime Direction, Ministry of Health and Social Protection, National Institute of Health and had the support and input from IOCARIBE and the ANCA group.

The IV HAB workshop, held virtually on October 7 and 8, 2020 focused on three thematic areas: health, environment and economy. Invited experts from Spain (**Beatriz Reguera**), Mexico (**Christine Band Schmidt**, **Erick Núñez Vázquez**) and Cuba (**Gustavo Arencibia**) shared their views and experience. The sessions were broadcast via YouTube, with more than 120 participants from Colombia and other countries in the region [1-2]

During the workshop a review of HAB seminars held in Colombia was presented (**Juliana Mancera**, CCO); as well as the main problems related to CP showing a historical analysis between 2010 and 2019 (**Milena Borbón Ramos**, National Institute of Health). The potential fish vector species in the Seaflower Biosphere Reserve where most Colombian cases of CP have occurred, were presented (**Adriana Santos-Martínez**, Universidad Nacional de Colombia), as well as the HABs impacts on the tourism sector (**Mónica Puyana Hegedus**, **Jorge Tadeo Lozano University**). The current capacities of the environmental sector (**Lu-**

isa Fernanda Espinosa, INVEMAR) and the development of risk indices of HABs (**José Ernesto Mancera Pineda**, ANCA) were detailed. Scientific and socioeconomic criteria were discussed for the design of early warning systems for HABs (**Beatriz Reguera**, Institute of Oceanography, **Vigo Oceanographic Center**) as well as guidelines for the generation of the early warning protocol in Colombia (**Joana Pérez**, National Unit for Disaster Risk Management).

The workshop was an opportunity to widely disseminate information about CP amongst a diverse audience, as well as to identify Colombian strengths and weaknesses to address the impacts from HABs. Among the strengths, the existence of a regulatory framework (Law 1523 of 2012) was highlighted. By implementing this law, Colombia adopted a disaster risk management policy and established the National Risk Management System. Risk management (RM) is understood as the process of planning, execution, monitoring and evaluation of actions to be aware of, avoid, reduce or control risks to avoid or mitigate disasters. The RM has the explicit purpose of contributing to the safety, well-being and quality of life of people and to sustainable development. Although in Colombia there are no management protocols or an early warning system regarding HABs, Law 1523 represents the legal framework

to develop a national plan for HAB management.

Another of the strengths identified in the country is the support of different organizations and public and private institutions interested in HABs, as well as the technical advice provided by different Colombian experts and international networks. Likewise, the experience gained with HAB research projects carried out so far, and the current activities such as the monitoring and the development of HAB risk indices, were recognized as an important advance.

Currently, INVEMAR is carrying out a monitoring project co-financed by the IAEA, in which the CIOH and the National Universities of Colombia and Cartagena participate. It is expected that the monitoring data will be useful to validate the IRAFAN index proposed by the IOCARIBE-ANCA group.

Among the weaknesses identified, the limited recognition of the potential negative impacts generated by HABs was highlighted. This is a matter of concern considering that the Caribbean development model is based mainly on tourism, an industry that each year reports a significant economic income. Fishing also provides an important source of protein for local communities. In this sense, HAB events and particularly CP represent a socioeconomic development problem.

It was concluded that the National Technical Committee on Marine Pollution should continue to lead this process. For this purpose, more support for financial resources for scientific research is required as well as more information for decision making; better fishing controls; training for the health sector and greater dissemination through different media.

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Luis Alfonso Vidal Velásquez (1950-2020) – In Memoriam

On November 8, 2020, Professor Luis Alfonso Vidal Velásquez, the academic authority on marine phytoplankton in Colombia, sadly passed away. Alfonso graduated as a Marine Biologist from Jorge Tadeo Lozano University and since then he dedicated his life to the study of marine phytoplankton. He completed his master's degree at Universidad Nacional de Colombia. His master's thesis was meritorious and became a guide book on estuarine phytoplankton of common use in many universities of the country.

Luis Alfonso taught at various universities in Colombia, participated in numerous courses on phytoplankton taxonomy, collaborated with activities of the ANCA-IOCARIBE Group, and was a mentor to many biologists. His charisma, discipline and ability to manipulate microalgae under the microscope and his profound acuity to infer biological information, made him a permanent source of reference. He made his own capillaries to be able to manipulate microalgae a few microns long, under the microscope. His human qualities and sensitivity to social problems made him highly appreciated by his students and colleagues.

Alfonso was a free spirit; he never accepted a permanent position because he wanted to be independent, even at the cost of his financial stability. He was a true gentleman, his kindness was his signature, and all the people who had the opportunity and the luck to meet him, remember this as his most characteristic trait.

Insensitive to the lure of material life, his universe was in a drop of seawater, where he could immerse himself and admire the true beauty of this world: the infinite forms of microscopic life, its elegance and variety. Both inside and

outside the laboratory, Alfonso kept his spirit as a child alive, and this is the most remarkable aspect of his legacy: never lose your amazement when you look at nature, because in each being there is a hidden beauty; and this was true when it came to people, he always saw the best in each one and celebrated it.

The death of Luis Alfonso leaves a huge void and saddens the entire Colombian scientific community, especially in marine sciences. Fortunately, Luis Alfonso leaves an indelible mark; his peace will be preserved in the hearts of the people who knew him. His scientific work was the cornerstone of phytoplankton studies in the country, and will continue to be so for a long time.

Our condolences to his wife Ligia, his daughter Anayanci and his son Josué.

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From issue # 45 (2012) onwards, all new HAN issues are accessible via e-pages. These plus all the previous HAN issues (HAN collection) can be downloaded as a PDF at: [IOC-HAN collection](#)

Masaaki Kodama – In Memoriam

Masaaki Kodama was born on September 7th, 1943 in Saitama Prefecture near Tokyo. He passed away on August 30th, 2020 at the age of 76 after more than six months in hospital. This was a big shock for all his colleagues, especially for those he had trained in toxin-chemistry. Dr. Kodama was awarded a doctoral degree from the University of Tokyo in 1972 and moved to Kitasato University as an associate professor. He started HAB research in Ofunato Bay, Sanriku, Japan in the late 1970s where he monitored PSP toxins in field populations of *Alexandrium tamarens* and shellfish. Kodama's detailed research opened new avenues to the physiology and chemistry of toxin production processes in dinoflagellates and diatoms, and to toxin accumulation and excretion in bivalves. Based on these studies, he found that PSP toxins are combined with nucleotides and are released by enzymes (ribonuclease RNase). He further developed modifications in toxin monitoring methods by introducing an ELISA assay method.

Dr. Kodama played a pioneering role in the development of HAB science in Western Pacific countries. His first international cooperation on HABs re-

search took place in Thailand in 1984, a country where PSP cases had occurred the previous year. He organized a mission comprised of four Japanese researchers, including ourselves, and collected samples in the innermost areas of the Gulf of Thailand (Figure 1). He confirmed the presence of PSP toxins in cultures of *Alexandrium tamiyavanichii* isolated by Ms. Suchana Wisesang (a pioneer on toxic dinoflagellate physiology in Thailand). The species was named by Dr. Enrique Balech after the name of another Thai scientist, Dr. Stichai Tamiyavanich who died from an accident during a toxic dinoflagellate sampling trip.

Dr. Kodama participated in various international HAB meetings, and especially in the 7th International Conference on Toxic Phytoplankton held in Sendai in 1995, where he or his co-workers presented seven papers on PSP, DSP, and ASP toxins in shellfish, and also a joint contribution, with local and international colleagues, about symbiosis of bacteria with toxic plankton. One evening, during that conference, he invited over 10 foreign participants to a bar for drinks and music. Figure 2 recalls Kodama's jolly attitude to music.

Fig. 2. Playing guitar during a break in the VII International Conference on Harmful Algae in Sendai, 1995. (Photo DM Anderson)

He had more than 30 different musical instruments, and often played them, even during conferences and sampling trips abroad.

After the Sendai Conference, he hosted a HAB training course in Kitasato University, with more than 30 invited scientists. His friendliness and easily

Fig. 1. Drs Masaaki Kodama, Yasuwo Fukuyo and Takehiko Ogata on a sampling trip at Pran Buri, Thailand. The man with a helmet on the left is Dr Tamiyavanich

Fig. 3. Having a discussion with Dr Rhodora Azanza during a training course in Kitasato University, July 1995

understandable lectures attracted all participants. Figure 3 shows him during a discussion about toxins with Dr. Rhodora Azanza, a participant from the Philippines. Dr. Kodama visited the Philippines quite often, because of the widely endemic PSP problems of that country. He joined a JICA (Japanese International Cooperation Agency) project to establish PSP toxin monitoring centers and joined seminars and training courses at various places organized by Mr. Cielito Gonzales of the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources. Figure 4 shows him during a break and giving a seminar for local staff working on toxin monitoring at an elementary school in the Philippines.

Domoic acid in bivalves was another of his research interests and a major issue at the time of his cooperative work in Vietnam. His collaborator there was Dr. Dao Viet Ha, currently the director of the Institute of Oceanography (Nha Trang, Vietnam). Dao Viet Ha thesis research was about identification of the phytoplankton species producers of domoic acid that contaminated shelfish at Phu Quoc Island. She was the last of Kodama's PhD students (Figure 5)

Outside Eastern Asia, he traveled to Central American countries (Guatemala and Puerto Rico) for PSP-related research. Figure 6 shows him bathing in a hot spring on the Atlantic coast of Guatemala during a sampling break, together with Guatemalan Coast Guard officers.

During the last years he had trouble

in walking and stayed at home. Sometimes we visited him and enjoyed talking on various HAB topics, especially on toxin producing bacteria and their contamination in organs of protists and animals. Figure 7 was taken together with Dr. Yasukatsu Oshima at his home. We pray that he rests in peace smiling as in the photo.

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Fig. 5. International cooperation on ASP toxicity in Vietnam. Graduation of Dr. Dao Viet Ha, currently the director of the Institute of Oceanography of Nha Trang, last PhD student of Kodama.

Fig. 6. Bathing in a hot spring, with the Coast Guard officers, Atlantic coast of Guatemala, during a sampling break.

Fig. 7. Dr Masaaki Kodama with Dr. Yasukatsu Oshima at Kodama's home.

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ISSHA's Corner

NEW DATE: October 10-15 2021

Hybrid Conference - Call for abstracts - ICHA 2021

Dear ISSHA members and colleagues,
The organizing committee is pleased to announce the call for abstracts for the *19th International Conference on Harmful Algal Blooms* to be held from the 10th to the 15th of October 2021 in the Conference Center of La Paz, B.C.S., Mexico. We will have a hybrid meeting, providing you the choice to participate either in person or remotely.

We invite the submission of abstracts within a broad range of topics related to the study of harmful algae, ranging from basic research to future applications. For the full list of topics, please visit the [conference website](#). The deadline for submitting an abstract for a poster, speed-talk or an oral presenta-

tion is **9 April 2021**. All abstracts must be submitted at the [conference website](#).

All ISSHA members who have already renewed their membership (after 1 October 2019) will remain active members until after the conference. If your membership has expired, please [renew your ISSHA membership](#). Your membership fees ensure that the conference is successful, and are used to help support student travel, awards, and plenary speakers. **Participants wishing to receive the ISSHA member rate for conference registration must join ISSHA or renew their memberships prior to 11 June 2021. Discounted membership is provided for students.**

A visa may be required for participants from some countries. Please check your country's visa requirements well in advance with your local Mexican Consulate for official instructions on the specific visa, travel regulations, and application procedures.

As the major host of the conference, ISSHA will support the following activities: student travel awards, achievement awards, and the popular ISSHA auction!

On behalf of the conference organizing committees, we look forward to receiving your submission.

Christine Band-Schmidt
Chair of ICHA 2021
[icha2021.com](http://www.icha2021.com)

Monitoring and preventing ciguatera poisoning

FAO-IAEA-IOC-WHO e-learning course

Ciguatera poisoning is one of the most common foodborne illnesses related to consumption of fishery products, caused by ingesting seafood that have been contaminated by ciguatoxins (CTXs). This course is designed to help learners understand the ecology of the causative organisms, as well as the potential hazard of fish contamination and consequent illnesses. The course proposes tools, approaches and strategies for the design and implementation of environmental, food safety and epidemiological monitoring, with a view to developing a well-informed ciguatera risk management plan.

The Course is now available online, as a global public good, through the FAO e-learning Academy: elearning.fao.org. Direct link to the course: <https://elearning.fao.org/course/view.php?id=648>

The FAO e-learning Academy is adopting the *Digital Badges Certification System*, to certify the acquisition of competencies, progress talents within organizations and increase employment opportunity.

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline

Deadline to submit material for HAN 67:
March 15th, 2021

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